

Deterministic Upper Bound on Expansive Phases in the Collatz Dynamics

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Abstract

We analyze the duration of consecutive expansive steps in the Collatz $(3x+1)$ trajectory. By examining the binary structure of integers, specifically the runs of trailing ones, we prove that the length of any maximal sequence of consecutive odd steps in the reduced map $T(n) = (3n+1)/2$ is strictly bounded by the binary length $L(n)$ of the starting integer.

For a number with k trailing ones (e.g., Mersenne numbers), the expansive phase lasts exactly $k-1$ steps, reaching a maximum duration of $k-1 = L(n) - 1$ in the boundary case $n = 2^k - 1$.

This establishes a sharp, deterministic $O(L(n))$ limit on how long a trajectory can remain in a strictly growth-favourable regime before a mandatory parity switch leads to a division by 2.

1 Introduction

The Collatz conjecture posits that the orbit of any $n \in \mathbb{N}$ under the map $f(n)$ reaches 1. A key difficulty lies in bounding the potential divergence of trajectories. While probabilistic models suggest that expansive steps are balanced by divisions, deterministic bounds are rare.

In this work, we prove that continuous ascent under the reduced Collatz map is structurally impossible to sustain beyond a fixed and predictable limit. We show that the duration of any continuous expansive phase is bounded by the information content (number of bits) of the starting value.

2 Preliminaries

Let $L(n) = \lfloor \log_2 n \rfloor + 1$ denote the binary length of $n \geq 1$.

We consider the **Reduced Collatz Map**:

$$T(n) = \frac{3n+1}{2}, \quad n \text{ odd.}$$

An “expansive phase” is a sequence of iterations

$$n_0 \mapsto n_1 = T(n_0) \mapsto n_2 = T(n_1) \mapsto \dots$$

in which all the n_i remain odd.

Definition 2.1 (Trailing ones). For an odd integer $n \geq 1$, let $\tau(n)$ denote the length of the terminal block of ones in the binary expansion of n . That is, if

$$n = m \cdot 2^k + (2^k - 1),$$

with m odd and $k \geq 1$, then $\tau(n) = k$.

Note that $\tau(n) \leq L(n)$, with equality if and only if n is a Mersenne number $2^L - 1$.

3 Main Structural Lemma

Lemma 3.1 (Decay of trailing ones under T). Let n be an odd integer with $\tau(n) = k \geq 1$. Then:

1. $T(n)$ is odd if and only if $k \geq 2$;

2. when $k \geq 2$, one has

$$\tau(T(n)) = k - 1.$$

Consequently, starting from n with $\tau(n) = k$, exactly $k - 1$ consecutive odd values are produced by iterating T before an even output necessarily appears.

Proof. Write $n = m \cdot 2^k + (2^k - 1)$ with m odd and $k = \tau(n) \geq 1$. Then:

$$3n + 1 = 3m \cdot 2^k + 3(2^k - 1) + 1 = 3m \cdot 2^k + (3 \cdot 2^k - 2).$$

The term $(3 \cdot 2^k - 2)$ equals

$$(11 \dots 10)_2 \quad (\text{with } k \text{ trailing zeros}).$$

The binary addition of $3m \cdot 2^k$ and $(3 \cdot 2^k - 2)$ induces a carry chain that propagates exactly through the k trailing ones of n , producing:

- divisibility by 2 but not by 4 when $k \geq 2$, and - divisibility by at least 4 when $k = 1$.

Thus:

$$v_2(3n + 1) = \begin{cases} 1, & k \geq 2, \\ \geq 2, & k = 1. \end{cases}$$

If $k = 1$, then $T(n)$ is even. If $k \geq 2$, division by 2 removes precisely one trailing one:

$$\tau(T(n)) = k - 1.$$

This proves both claims. □

4 Main Theorem

Theorem 4.1 (Length of Expansive Phases). Let n_0 be an odd integer. Let $K_{\text{exp}}(n_0)$ denote the number of consecutive odd values generated by iteratively applying T . Then:

$$K_{\text{exp}}(n_0) = \max\{\tau(n_0) - 1, 0\} \leq L(n_0) - 1.$$

Moreover, $K_{\text{exp}}(n_0) = L(n_0) - 1$ if and only if n_0 is a Mersenne number $2^{L(n_0)} - 1$.

Proof. By Lemma 3.1, an odd value n with $\tau(n) = k$ produces exactly $k - 1$ more odd outputs before the first even value appears, and $\tau(T(n)) = k - 1$ for each of these steps.

Thus:

$$K_{\text{exp}}(n_0) = \tau(n_0) - 1.$$

Since $\tau(n_0) \leq L(n_0)$ with equality if and only if n_0 is Mersenne, the bound follows. □

Corollary 4.2 (No Infinite Uninterrupted Growth). No Collatz trajectory can remain in an uninterrupted growth regime indefinitely. Every expansive phase has finite duration, bounded by the current binary length of the integer. Any divergent trajectory would therefore require an infinite sequence of Mersenne-like reconstructions.

5 Discussion

The main theorem shows that the “fuel” for continuous ascent—the terminal block of ones—decays deterministically and cannot exceed the binary length $L(n)$.

Remark (Dissipative residues). Once the expansive phase ends, the integer enters a regime of divisions by 2 whose intensity depends on the residue class of $n \pmod 8$:

- if $n \equiv 1 \pmod 8$ then $3n + 1$ is divisible by 4, - if $n \equiv 5 \pmod 8$ then $3n + 1$ is divisible by 8, - if $n \equiv 3 \pmod 8$ then $T(n)$ returns to $\equiv 1$ or $5 \pmod 8$.

These classes tend to accelerate dissipation after the expansive phase. This remark is not needed for the proof of Theorem 4.1 but helps clarify why long-term runaway behaviour would require highly structured oscillations.

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References

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